

INDEPENDENT AND JOINT EFFECTS OF THE LEVEL OF CONVERGENCE AND DIGITAL PRODUCTS

Pardayev O'ktam Berdimurodovich

Researcher of Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686861>

Abstract: The article shows the business model of joint business organization within the framework of convergence and the modeling bases of convergence processes. In business organization, it is justified that convergence has a significant impact on the development of convergence of business companies. The business foundations of the convergence of regional districts have been developed in the conditions of the digital economy.

Keywords: Convergence framework, joint business organization, business model, convergence processes, divergence, optimal order, company merger, Financial convergence, system efficiency.

The independent and combined effect of the degree of convergence and digitalization products can have not only positive, but also certain negative consequences. Therefore, the formation of a complete list of possible directions for increasing the efficiency of joint business includes the following activities in advance:

- to identify all potential opportunities to increase efficiency in connection with the characteristics of the level of economic convergence and the use of a certain digital product, including relevant conditions, factors and the content of the business organization itself;
- identify possible negative consequences of economic convergence and digitization effects that may adversely affect joint business performance;
- development of management decisions aimed at reducing possible negative consequences;
- assessment of the possible actual result of the joint business, i.e. comparing the efficiency gains due to the possible positive effects of convergence and digitization with the decrease in efficiency due to the possible negative effects.

The result of this analysis will be a list of joint business activities, the development of which will increase its effectiveness.

Developed below an algorithm for creating an initial set of all possible routes to increase the efficiency of joint business, which is carried out within a certain level of convergence when using a specific digitalization product.

The sequence of actions of this algorithm includes the following four steps:

1. clarify the considered level of economic convergence for which the

joint business will be established and the specific digitization product used within it;

2. define a list of prerequisites, factors and values of business model parameters for the level of convergence in question and the specific digitization product used in it;

3. determine the characteristics of the content of the necessary conditions, factors and parameters of the business model;

4. creating a list of all possible ways to increase joint business efficiency (based on the analysis of the content of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, taking into account the risk assessment of the interaction between economic convergence and digitization).).

The initial set obtained as a result of the presented algorithm is used to select specific directions for increasing business efficiency.

In general, the analysis showed the following.

The characteristics of the interaction between the level of convergence and digitization lead to different contents of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, which, in turn, determines the feasibility of clarifying their contents under the influence of different levels of economic convergence. various digital products. Convergence and digitization processes can affect joint business efficiency in different ways, so it is necessary to take this fact into account when forming a list of possible directions for increasing its efficiency.

In addition, the following should be noted. In general, since digitalization can have both positive and negative effects on the processes of economic convergence, this fact should be taken into account when identifying all possible directions for increasing efficiency. The real size of the positive effect of one or another direction of efficiency improvement, usually measured in monetary terms, between the potential, the maximum possible economic effect resulting from the introduction of the considered direction of efficiency improvement should be defined as a difference. costs associated with obtaining it. At the same time, the possible negative consequences measured in monetary units are a considered way to increase efficiency. should be taken into account among the costs of implementing the system, i.e. possible negative effects of digitization should be taken into account.

Later on. When choosing a criterion of joint business efficiency, the initiator first of all raises the question of whether the chosen criterion of efficiency ensures the achievement of its goal - to increase its competitiveness. This means that

whatever criterion is chosen for joint business effectiveness, it should be related to solving the problem of increasing the competitiveness of the initiator of joint business creation.

Additional requirements for building an effective joint venture include:

- business efficiency should be calculated taking into account not only positive, but also possible negative effects of digitalization on economic convergence processes;
- the search for the most effective methods of increasing efficiency should be based on all possible areas characterized by a certain degree of convergence, provided that a certain digital product is used in it.

As mentioned above, the list of all possible directions for improving business efficiency, determined by the content of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, is the interaction between a certain level of economic convergence and specific digitization. related to the characteristics of the secret. product. Note that the algorithm for creating an initial set of all possible directions for increasing business efficiency, which is carried out within a certain level of convergence when using a certain digitization product, includes:

- determining the level of economic convergence at which the joint venture will be established and the specific digitization product used within it;
 - determine the relevant list of prerequisites, factors and values of business model parameters;
 - determine the characteristics of the content of the determined conditions, factors and parameters of the business model;
- making a list of all possible ways to improve joint business efficiency.

References:

1. Mukhitdinov Khudayar Suyunovich, Pardayev O'ktam Berdimurodovich, Rahimov Odil Berdievich, "AGRICULTURE CLUSTER IMPLEMENTATION IN A PRODUCTION SYSTEM", JOURNAL OF NORTHEASTERN UNIVERSITY, 2022/11/16, ст 1092-1106, ISSN: 1005-3026
2. Suyunovich, Mukhitdinov Khudoyar, and Norqobilova Feruza Abdihamidovna. "Prospects Of Digitalization Of Craftsmanship Development In The Region." Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results (2022): 345-352.
3. Норқобилова, Ф. А. "ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШ ТАРМОҚЛАРИНИ МОДЕЛЛАШТИРИШДА ТИЗИМЛИ ТАҲЛИЛ ҚИЛИШ, СИНТЕЗЛАШ ВА ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ." International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online). Vol. 1. No. 2. 2021.

4. Abdihamidovna, Norqobilova Feruza. "Financial Services to the Residents of the Region in the Field of Crafts." *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology* 1.5 (2021): 225-230.
5. Қодиров, Фаррух, et al. "АҲОЛИГА СОҒЛИҚНИ САҚЛАШ ХИЗМАТЛАРИ КЎРСАТИШДАН ОЛИНГАН ДАРОМАДЛАРНИНГ ЭКОНОМЕТРИК МОДЕЛИ." *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot* 2.4 (2023): 110-122.
6. Qodirov, Farrux, et al. "SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARI SIFATI VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH BORASIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR." *Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya* 2.4 (2023): 66-72.
7. Qodirov, Farrux, et al. "SEZUVCHI SENSORLAR VA HARAKATNI TA'MINLOVCHI SENSORLARNING ROBOTOTEXNIKADAGI O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI." *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences* 2.3 (2023): 27-34.
8. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "CREATION OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL BASE WITH THE HELP OF SOFTWARE PACKAGES FOR MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." *Conferencea* (2022): 128-130.
9. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "IMPORTANCE OF KASH-HEALTH WEB PORTAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." *Conferencea* (2022): 80-83.
10. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш ўгли. "Ижтимоий ва хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришда соғлиқни сақлаш хизматларини эконометрик моделлаштиришнинг аҳамияти", Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар Академияси ЎЗР ФА бирлашган касаба уюшма кўмитаси Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар академияси ёш олимлар кенгаши, 2022/9/30, ст-211-213.
11. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш ўгли. "Вилоят аҳолисига соғлиқни сақлаш хизматлари кўрсатиш тармоқлари ривожланиш механизмининг статистик таҳлили". "Innovatsion texnologiyalar, IT-texnologiya va ishlab chiqarishda mehnat muhofazasi muommolari va yechimlari" mavzusida xorijiy hamkorlar ishtirokida Respublika ilmiy- amaliy anjuman materiallari, 2022/9/23, ст-540-545.
12. Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li. "Optimum solutions for the development of medical services in private clinics", *Raqamli transformatsiya jarayoniga axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etishda ma'lumotlarni himoyalash muammolari va yechimlari respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani ma'ruzalar to'plami*, 2022/5/13, ст 79-82.

13. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш ўғли, “Худудларда тиббий хизмат кўрсатишни эмпирик моделлаштириш”, ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ, 2022, ст-119-123.
14. Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, “Аҳолига тиббий хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасининг келгуси ҳолатини башоратлаш”, “Сервис” илмий-амалий журнал, 2022, ст 56-59.
15. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш угли, “Қашқадарё вилояти аҳолисига тиббий хизмат кўрсатиш тармоқларини ривожлантиришнинг истиқболлари”, AGRO ILM – O‘ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ VA SUV XO‘JALIGI, 2022, ст 119-120.
16. Маматмурадова, М. У., И. Ж. Бозорова, and Ф. Э. Кодиров. "СОЗДАНИЕ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И РЕСУРСОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В НЕПРЕРЫВНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2019.
17. Абдирасулов, Ж. У., and Ф. Э. Кодиров. "СТРУКТУРНЫЕ СОСТАВЛЕНИЯ МОБИЛЬНОЙ ОПЕРАЦИОННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ANDROID И ЕЕ ЯДРО." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2019.
18. Qodirov, F. E., et al. "OVER VIEW FROM YII 2 FRAMEWORKS, AND ALSO ITS ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES." СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ПОЗНАНИЯ В ЦЕЛЯХ РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ (2019): 39.
19. Qodirov, F. E., et al. "PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE PROTECTION AGAINST NETWORK ATTACKS." НАУКОЕМКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ КАК ОСНОВА ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ (2019): 93.
20. Qodirov, Farrux Ergashevich, Shoxrux Ramazonov, and Husniya Rustamovna Salimova. "CONTROL OVER SYSTEM" SMART HOUSE" WITH THE HELP OF WIRELESS NETWORK." НАУЧНАЯ ДИСКУССИЯ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МОЛОДЁЖИ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ. 2019.
21. Qodirov, F. E., et al. "ESSENCE OF THE NOTION ELECTRONIC DICTIONARY." КОНЦЕПЦИЯ" ОБЩЕСТВА ЗНАНИЙ" В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ. 2019.
22. Qodirov, F. E., et al. "FEATURES OF INTEL CORE i9 X-SERIES PROCESSORS AND ITS ADVANTAGE FROM OTHER PROCESSORS." ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНОСТИ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ НАУЧНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. 2019.
23. Ахматова, С. З., М. Б. Шамсиддинов, and Ж. Р. Орзикулов. "ФЭ Қодиров." 72.

24. ФЭ Қодиров, ЗА Мансурова, МБ Шамсиддинов. "КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫЕ ИГРЫ И ИХ ТЕКУЩИЕ ВИДЫ И ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА" ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ НАУЧНОЙ ..., 2019: ст 59-61
25. Элчаев, З. А., et al. "КОНТРОЛИРОВАНИЕ НАД СИСТЕМОЙ" УМНЫЙ ДОМ" С ПОМОЩЬЮ БЕСПРОВОДНОГО СЕТЯ." ПРОРЫВНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ КАК ДВИГАТЕЛЬ НАУКИ. 2019.
26. ФЭ Қодиров, ШУ Рамазонов, СЗ Ахматова. "РАЗРАБОТКА ВИДЕОИГРЫ НА ПЛАТФОРМЕ UNITY 3D" ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ КАК ФАКТОР, 2019: ст 56-91
27. FE Kodirov, SZ Axmatova. "LiFi-NEW NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES" НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИИ В XXI ВЕКЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ..., 2019: ст 99-101
28. Юсупов, Ш. Ш., Ж. Э. Нематов, and Ф. Э. Қодиров. "О ПРИНЦИПАХ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ОРГАНИЗОВАННЫХ СИСТЕМ." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2018.
29. Ахматова, С. З., and Ф. Э. Қодиров. "МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ДИНАМИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМ НА ПРОГРАММУ MICROSOFT EXCEL." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2018.
30. Turdiyev, U. Q., and F. E. Kodirov. "INTRODUCTION OF DERIVED OF FUNCTION OF COMPUTER SOFTWARE PRODUCTS TO ENABLE READER THROUGH THE USE OF CASE STUDIES." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2018.
31. Турдиев, У. К., and Ф. Э. Кодиров. "ЗАДАЧА КОШИ ДЛЯ ОДНОМЕРНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УРАВНЕНИЙ ТИПА БЮРГЕРСА ВОЗНИКАЮЩЕЙ В ДВУХСКОРОСТНОЙ ГИДРОДИНАМИКЕ." Инновации в технологиях и образовании. 2018.
32. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux, and Berdiyev Sardor Sobir o'g'li. "DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL APPLICATIONS IN THE PROGRAM OF EXISTING SCRIPT LANGUAGE."
33. FE Qodirov, MA Turdiyeva, DB Eshmurodova. "VALUE OF WEBSITES FOR SUCCESSFULLY STARTING STARTUP" - ИСТОРИЯ, СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ..., 2020 ст-135-136
34. Qodirov, F. E., J. B. Zoxidov, and M. A. Turdiyeva. "DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATIC VENTILATION SYSTEM FOR SMART GREENHOUSES." Теории, школы и концепции устойчивого развития науки в современных условиях. 2020.
35. Jumanazarovna, Bozorova Irina, and Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li. "ПРИНЦИП РАБОТЫ ЭЛЕКТРОКАРДИОГРАФА И ЕГО РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ

МЕДИЦИНЕ." НАУЧНЫЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ И УЧАЩИХСЯ: сборник статей (2020): 25.

36. Qalandarov, Vazirbek Nasriddinovich, and Saera Jetkerbaevna Barlikbaeva. "CURRENT ROLE AND DISADVANTAGES OF QR-CODE TECHNOLOGY." НАУЧНЫЕ ТРУДЫ МОЛОДЫХ УЧЁНЫХ. 2020.

37. FE Qodirov, MA Turdiyeva, YQ Shoniyozova. "PAYMENT BASED ON THE QR CODE TECHNOLOGY, ITS ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES" ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ, ПРОВЕДЕНИЕ И ..., 2020: ст3-4.

38. Abdirasulov, Javohir. "Axborot texnologiyalari Axborot texnologiyalari haqida." Архив научных исследований (2020).

39. ҚОДИРОВ, ФАРРУХ ЭРГАШ ЎҒЛИ, ҲУСНИЯ РУСТАМОВНА САЛИМОВА, and ЖАХАР РАИМКУЛ ЎҒЛИ ОРЗИКУЛОВ. "ЗАЩИТА ИНФОРМАЦИИ В КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ СЕТЯХ." Наука среди нас 4 (2019): 222-228.

40. Qodirov, F. E., D. A. Akbarova, and S. H. Shokirov. "SOFTWARE FOR WORKING WITH COMPUTER GRAPHICS AND THEIR TASKS. APPLICATION OF DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING FIELDS." Инновации в технологиях и образовании: сб. ст. участников XIV Меж (2021): 57.

41. ЖУ Абдирасулов, ФЭ Қодиров, ЮК Шониёзова. "ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВЕБ-САЙТОВ ДЛЯ УСПЕШНО ЗАПУСКА СТАРТАПОВ" Инновации в технологиях и образовании, 2020: Ст 26-28

42. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux, and Bozorova Irina Jumanazarovna. "METHODS OF DISPLAYING MAIN MEMORY ON CACHE." Ответственный редактор (2020):

43. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux, and Bozorova Irina Jumanazarovna. "MODERN PROGRAMMING TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR ROLE." ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫЙ КАПИТАЛ XXI ВЕКА: сборник статей II Международного (2020): 19.

44. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "IMPORTANCE OF KASH-HEALTH WEB PORTAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 80-83.

45. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш ўгли. "Ижтимоий ва хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришда соғлиқни сақлаш хизматларини эконометрик моделлаштиришнинг аҳамияти", Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар Академияси ЎЗР ФА бирлашган қасаба уюшма қўмитаси Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар академияси ёш олимлар кенгаши, 2022/9/30, ст-211-213.

46. Қодиров Фаррух Эргаш ўгли. “Вилоят аҳолисига соғлиқни сақлаш хизматлари кўрсатиш тармоқлари ривожланиш механизмининг статистик таҳлили”. “Innovatsion texnologiyalar, IT-texnologiya va ishlab chiqarishda mehnat muhofazasi muammolari va yechimlari” mavzusida xorijiy hamkorlar ishtirokida Respublika ilmiy- amaliy anjuman materiallari, 2022/9/23, сt-540-545.

47. Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li. “Optimum solutions for the development of medical services in private clinics”, Raqamli transformatsiya jarayoniga axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etishda ma'lumotlarni himoyalash muammolari va yechimlari respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani ma'ruzalar to'plami, 2022/5/13, сt 79-82.

